

Memorandum in response to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

To the Clerk of the Committee of Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

I am writing in regards to the proposed Ghanaian Values Bill as a concerned Ghanaian diasporan who has recently moved back to Accra. I am highly shocked at what this bill proposes, for this is not the Ghana I envisioned returning to. I am very proud of my nationality, and after living abroad in many different countries I feel I have represented my country very well and always encouraged others to learn more about our culture and society, even encouraging many peers and friends to visit. However, what this bill proposes has me questioning my pride in my country. This bill is an extreme violation of human rights, not just towards the LGBT community, who are indeed citizens of this great country, but also to society as a whole. It attacks right of privacy, freedom of speech and will only incite further violence against Ghanaian citizens from the LGBT community. It directly goes against our constitution and calls for bringing about laws which have no place in Ghanaian culture. These homophobic laws and attitudes are a colonial relic, and in order for us to continue moving forward as a people we cannot reinforce old laws that divide us. If this bill is passed, I fear we will only regress as a society. I am still dedicated to returning to Ghana with the knowledge I have earned abroad in order to better my country, all I ask is that you continue to make this great country one I am proud to serve; one in which we all work together to create a loving and just society, not one that divides us through hate and fear.

Regards,

K [REDACTED] D [REDACTED]